

**NUMERACY SKILL, LEARNING STYLE, AND LEARNING ENGAGEMENT OF
STUDENTS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE:
BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT**

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Numeracy Skill, Learning Style, and Learning Engagement of Students in Relation to Academic Performance: Basis for Enhancement

Joeveline P. Chrisman*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study determined the numeracy skill, learning style, and learning engagement of Grade 9 students in relation to their academic performance in the District 3B, Division of Bacolod City for S.Y. 2023-2024. Three hundred four Grade 9 students were the respondents of the study. Their numeracy skill was taken from the Mid E-RUNT result. A standardized questionnaire on the learning style of students and a modified questionnaire to measure the learning engagement of Grade 9 were used in this study. The results of the study were as follows: most of the students were numerates, displayed a kinesthetic learning style, have a high level of learning engagement, and obtained a very satisfactory academic performance. There was a significant relationship between the numeracy skills of Grade 9 students and their academic performance, and between the level of learning engagement and their academic performance. However, there was no significant relationship between the learning style and the academic performance of students. It is recommended to implement focused numeracy programs like tutoring after-school programs, summer math classes, and incorporating numeracy exercises into normal classroom procedures. Teachers may use individualized instruction adapted to how their students learn (visual, auditory, and kinesthetic) to improve understanding and retention of material. Teachers were encourage to continue in providing active learning and student involvement, and use active learning tactics including group projects, interactive activities, and technological integration to boost student participation. School administrators may continue to provide professional development for teachers by offering programs that focus on effective numeracy teaching practices, supporting varied learning styles, and enhancing student engagement.

Keywords: *numeracy skill, learning style, learning engagement, academic performance*

Introduction

The study of numeracy skills, learning styles and student engagement presents a complex and multifaceted interplay that is critical to educational success. Acquiring numeracy is a fundamental skill that students must develop early in their education, as it involves a confident grasp of numerical identification, counting proficiency, recognition of numerical patterns, the execution of basic operations and problem-solving strategies, and the ability to employ these skills in grasping more intricate mathematical concepts. Educators, from the formative years of students, introduce them to the foundational elements of problem-solving, emphasizing its application as an essential skill for everyday life. Mastery of these competencies is crucial for a deeper comprehension and progression in the field of Mathematics (Pitogo & Oco, 2023).

According to UNICEF 2022, between 2020 and 2022, over half of the 147 million children who were supposed to receive in-person education were not enrolled. UNICEF warns that many people, especially the most vulnerable, are at risk of giving up on education altogether, resulting in the lowest probability of being literate in reading, writing, and basic math. UNICEF stated that in the nations studied, the current rate of learning is so slow that most schoolchildren would need eleven years to learn the basic numeracy skills. The performance of our students in large scale assessment, the National Achievement Test, which was administer for Grade 6, Grade 10 and Grade 12, gravitates towards the low proficiency levels especially in Science, Math and English. In 2018, DepEd boldly decided to participate for the first time in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) of the organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The PISA results, where we placed last among 79 participating countries and near last in science and mathematics, puts in even sharper focus our need to address quality in basic education (Briones, 2019).

In parallel, the concept of learning styles is recognized as a significant factor in education, influencing both the learning journey and the classroom atmosphere. Learning styles, which are unique to each individual, shape the way students engage with educational content. The most frequently recognized learning styles are visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. It is crucial for teachers to comprehend these learning preferences to adapt their instructional strategies, thereby enhancing the learning experience for their students (Dmitrichenkova, 2020).

Furthermore, student engagement, which refers to how interested, motivated, and involved a student is in their learning, plays a crucial role in determining educational success. Various factors can influence student engagement, such as the relevance of the material, the teaching methods used, and the classroom environment. True engagement is essential for effective learning, as it helps students absorb information and perform well academically; therefore, understanding the importance of student engagement is critical (Thompson, 2023).

This study aimed to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by analyzing how these variables—numeracy skills, learning styles, and student engagement—interact and influence student performance in numeracy. The interconnections between these elements are

essential for educators to understand in order to foster a conducive learning environment that promotes both academic achievement and personal growth.

Research Questions

This study determined the numeracy skill, learning style, and learning engagement of Grade 9 students in relation to their academic performance in the District 3B, Division of Bacolod City for S.Y. 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the status of numeracy skill of Grade 9 students?
2. What is the common learning styles of Grade 9 students when taken in terms of:
 - 2.1. visual;
 - 2.2. auditory;
 - 2.3. read/write; and
 - 2.4. kinesthetic?
3. What is the level of learning engagement of Grade 9 students?
4. What is the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students?
5. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their numeracy skill?
6. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their learning style?
7. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their learning engagement?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the level of numeracy skill of Grade 9 students and their academic performance?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the learning styles of Grade 9 students and their academic performance?
10. Is there a significant relationship between the learning engagement of Grade 9 students and their academic performance?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized the descriptive correlational research design. As stated by Chaudhari (2021) descriptive research is used to collect information about the current state of phenomena and to depict what is present in terms of variables or conditions within a particular situation. Descriptive research is often used in education and is useful for investigating status. Its importance stems from the conviction that issues can be resolved and procedures may be improved by observation, analysis, and description. Moreover, this study sought to find out the numeracy skill, learning style, and learning engagement of Grade 9 students in relation to their academic performance.

Respondents

The subject and respondents of this study were the Grade 9 students at 6 public secondary schools in the Division of Bacolod City, School Year 2023-2024. The Grade 9 students from the different public secondary schools in the Division of Bacolod City has a population of 1,260 students. The researcher used the Yamane's Formula to get the sample size of the population with a margin of error of 5%.

The researcher used the stratified random sampling technique to determine the respondents per school. Then, simple random sampling technique through lottery method was used to identify respondents taken as samples. Table on the next page shows the distribution of the respondents per school.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Sample and Number of Enrollees per School*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>No. of Enrollees</i>	<i>Sample</i>
A	130	31
B	171	41
C	450	109
D	103	25
E	95	23
F	311	75
Total	1,260	304

Instrument

A standardized questionnaire was used to assess the learning engagement of the students. This was adopted from the study of Imran, Khan and Aslam (2023) entitled "Development and Validation of Student Engagement Questionnaire". It is composed of 20 statements describing the engagement of the students in their learning. Each item can be measured using Likert scale using 1 as strongly disagree, 2 as disagree, 3 as neither agree nor disagree, 4 as agree and 5 as strongly agree. To measure the learning style of the students, the VARK Questionnaire (Version 8.01) was adopted. It is categorized as visual, auditory, read/write, and kinesthetic. There are 16 items

that has 4 options each. The responses of the students as to what learning style they are using was based on the scoring chart found in the Appendix E.

The Midyear Enhanced-Regional Unified Numeracy Test (ERUNT) was used to measure the numeracy skill of the students. It is an assessment tool used by the Department of Education in the Philippines to evaluate the numeracy skills of students from Grades 1 to 11 learners in all private and public schools. For Grade 9 students, the E-RUNT focuses on assessing their proficiency in the four fundamental operations of mathematics: addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division of integers and understanding numbers and problem-solving as well (DepEd RM 1092, s. 2023). It is conducted three times a school year: a pre-test, a mid-test, and a post-test. The results help identify students who need additional support and guide the implementation of intervention programs to improve their numeracy skills.

To measure the academic performance of the students, their average grades in the first and second quarter was used. The computation of the grades was based on the Dep.Ed Order number 8, series of 2015.

Procedure

The researcher sent a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent (see Appendix B.1) and different Principals of Public Secondary Schools in the Division of Bacolod City (see Appendix B.2) to ask permission that a study on “Numeracy Skill, Learning Style, and Learning Engagement of Students in Relation to Academic Performance: Basis for Enhancement” will be conducted.

As soon as the Superintendent and Principals approved the letter, the researcher sent a letter to the Grade 9 Class Advisers of different Public Secondary Schools to ask permission that this study be conducted to their students. After the approval, the researcher set a schedule from the Grade 9 Class Advisers on the availability of the respondents to answer the survey questionnaires. The gathered data were tallied, organized, presented and interpreted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis

The data were retrieved, encoded, and processed using SPSS. The statistical tools that the researcher used were:

For statement of the problem 1, which sought to determine the numeracy skill of Grade 9 students, the frequency and percent distribution were used.

For statement of the problem 2, which sought determine the common learning styles of Grade 9 students when taken in terms of visual, auditory, read/write, and kinesthetic, the frequency and percent distribution were used.

For statement of the problem 3, which sought to determine the level of learning engagement of Grade 9 students, mean was used.

For statement of the problem 4, which sought to determine the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students, mean was used.

For statement of the problem 6, which sought to determine if there is a significant difference in the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their learning style, Kruskal Wallis was used.

For statement of the problem 7, which sought to determine if there is a significant difference in the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their learning engagement, Kruskal Wallis was used.

For statement of the problem 8, which sought to determine if there is a significant relationship between the numeracy skill of Grade 9 students and their academic performance, chi-square test was used.

For statement of the problem 9, which sought to determine if there is a significant relationship between the learning style and the academic performance of Grade 9 students, chi-square test was used.

For statement of the problem 10, which sought to determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of learning engagement of Grade 9 students and their academic performance, Goodman Kruskal’s Gamma or Gamma Coefficient was used

Results and Discussion

This section underscores the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered in this research study.

Numeracy Skills of Students

The table below presents the status of the numeracy skills of Grade 9 students.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Numeracy Skills of Grade 9 Students*

<i>Numeracy Skills</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Numerate	245	80.60
Non-Numerate	59	19.40
Total	304	100.00

Based on the table, out of 304 total respondents, 245 or 80.60 percent of students are numerates while 59 or 19.40 percent are non-numerates. This implies that most of the students are proficient in utilizing mathematical concepts to solve practical problems and understand basic arithmetic operations. They have the ability to use, comprehend, and communicate mathematical information in order to solve real-world problems. This includes understanding fundamental arithmetic operations including addition, subtraction, division, and multiplication.

The findings of this study agree to the statement of Yako (2019) that poor numeracy skills can have a negative impact on educational outcomes, lowering opportunities for success in fields that need mathematical comprehension, such as science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) These students may have difficulty with simple activities, including personal handling of finances, data interpretation, and educated decision-making are all critical skills in today's environment. Addressing these gaps through targeted interventions and assistance is crucial to enhancing their academic achievement and providing them with the required skills to overcome daily obstacles.

Learning Styles of Students

The table below shows the learning styles of Grade 9 students.

Table 3. *Common Learning Styles of Grade 9 Students*

<i>Learning Styles</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Kinesthetic	180	59.20
Visual	73	24.00
Read/Write	28	9.20
Auditory	23	7.60
Total	304	100.00

Table 3 shows the learning styles of Grade 9 students. Out of the 304 respondents, 180 or 59.20 percent of them are kinesthetic, 73, or 24.00 percent are visual, 28 or 9.20 percent display a read and write learning style, and 23 or 7.60 percent are auditory.

The findings of this study reveal that majority of the respondents prefer a kinesthetic learning style followed by visual learners, read and write learners, and auditory learners. This means that they learn best through hands-on experiences and physical activities. They are likely to engage deeply with practical tasks, experiments, and other activities that involve movement and doing. A significant portion of the respondents are visual learners. These individuals learn best through visual aids such as diagrams, charts, videos, and written instructions. They benefit from seeing information presented visually. A smaller group of respondents prefers a read and write learning style. These learners excel when engaging with text-based materials, such as reading articles, writing notes, and working with lists and definitions. They tend to thrive in environments where they can read and write to process information. The smallest group of respondents consists of auditory learners. These individuals learn best through listening. They benefit from lectures, discussions, podcasts, and other auditory forms of information delivery.

The findings of this study are in consonance with the claim of Yako (2019) that kinesthetic learners benefit significantly from hands-on activities, tests, and simulations that allow them to physically interact with the information. This is especially important for adolescents in Grade 9, who are in a developmental period where physical activity is required for mental and emotional growth (KHAN et al., 2020). The findings suggest that visual learners get information more efficiently through sight. They benefit from diagrams, charts, videos, and written directions. In Grade Nine, visual Students may benefit from classes that use visual aids such as graphs, maps, and infographics. Color-coded notes, highlighters, and spatial organizing schemes may be preferable for arranging information. Visual learning aids can assist Grade 9 students receive and retain material more effectively, particularly in classes that involve complex thinking (Pendon, 2022).

Moreover, Staff (2023) states that understanding how students acquire knowledge through various means is critical in teaching. Educators can build more successful learning environments by adapting teaching approaches to the preferences of their pupils. Learning styles cover the numerous approaches people use to comprehend and recall information, allowing educators to create course materials that are tailored to their students' preferences (Escuadro, 2023).

Thus, identifying learners' styles allows for the customization of learning experiences to meet their particular preferences, ultimately leading to improved performance outcomes (Escuadro 2023). Recognizing and comprehending learners' individual styles is critical for optimizing the learning process and performance outcomes. Learners may use a variety of styles, including visual, aural, kinesthetic, tactile, and social learning. Identifying specific learning styles allows educators to adjust instructional design to provide effective learning experiences that address individual needs. While the assumption that learning styles are the best method to student learning has been debunked in recent years, they are nevertheless extensively used in education to respect diversity (GCU, 2020).

Furthermore, Yako (2019) also agreed to the findings of this study that the reading and writing, gain immensely from textbooks, articles, written assignments, and thorough note-taking. In Grade 9, these children may thrive in language arts and social studies, both of which require Extensive reading and writing. Encourage read/write learners to connect with information by assigning lengthy reading and writing projects, which can improve comprehension and analytical skills. While auditory learners learn best through listening, they can benefit from lectures, discussions, and audio materials such as podcasts. In Grade 9, auditory learners may do better if they participate

in group discussions.

Level of Student Learning Engagement

The table on the next page shows the level of student learning engagement of Grade 9 students.

Table 4. Level of Learning Engagement of Grade 9 Students

<i>Level of Student Learning Engagement</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	56		
High	184		
Moderate	59	3.79	High
Low	5		
Very Low	0		
Total	304		

The table shows the level of engagement of Grade 9 students: the very high level has a frequency of 56, the high level has a frequency of 184, the moderate level has a frequency of 59, and only five have low level of engagement. The mean score of the learning engagement of the Grade 9 students is 3.79 and is interpreted as high.

The results imply that the Grade 9 students show great amount of attention, interest, excitement, optimism, and passion that students show when learning or being taught. They were actively involved in the learning process, indicating the extent to which they find the learning experience successful. Engagement is especially critical for Grade 9 students, as they advance academically and confront more social expectations. High levels of engagement are frequently associated with active participation in classroom activities, a willingness to put forth effort in learning, and a positive attitude toward education.

The findings of this study are in agreement with the discovery of Otoum (2021) that making learning more relevant and interesting can enhance engagement. Furthermore, fostering a supportive and inclusive classroom climate in which students feel valued and appreciated can significantly boost engagement. Teachers that actively seek to understand and incorporate their students' interests and real-world applications into the curriculum are more likely to keep Grade 9 students interested, resulting in more effective learning and personal development (Brew et al., 2021).

Level of Academic Performance

The table below shows the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students.

Table 5. Level of Academic Performance of Grade 9 Students

<i>Level of Academic Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding	75		
Very Satisfactory	105		
Satisfactory	100	85.96	Very Satisfactory
Fairly Satisfactory	24		
Did Not Meet Expectations	0		
Total	304		

Based on the table above, the level of academic performance of students in Grade 9 is as follows: there are 75 students who have an outstanding academic performance, 105 students have a very satisfactory academic performance, 100 have a satisfactory rating, and 24 who have a fairly satisfactory academic performance. The mean performance of the 304 respondents is 85.96 and is interpreted as very satisfactory.

The result indicates that the Grade 9 students, on average, have achieved a very satisfactory level of performance. They have met or exceeded the expected standards or criteria for success. They are performing very well in their academics. They exhibit eagerness to learn the subject and attain good grades. By continuing to support and enhance the learning or performance environment, the goal of the school can be to maintain or even surpass this commendable level of achievement.

The findings are consistent with the Landicho (2021) study, which shows that students are motivated to learn the material and get good scores. A student's enthusiasm in mathematics is essential to learning mathematical concepts and abilities, which makes it a critical component of attaining academic success in mathematics. The study also reveals a positive relationship between students' interest in learning and their academic achievement, offering insights into the function of academic interest in a variety of subject areas.

Difference in the Academic Performance of Students when they are grouped according to their Numeracy Skill

The table below shows the difference in the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their numeracy skill.

Based on the table below, the 245 numerate students obtained a mean rank of 162.23 while the 59 non-numerate obtained a mean rank

of 112.08.

Table 6. Difference in the Academic Performance of Students when they are grouped according to their Numeracy Skill

Numeracy Skills	n	Mean Rank
Numerate	245	162.23
Non-Numerate	59	112.08
Total	304	

Computed value (U): 4842.50

p-value: <0.001

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Mann Whitney, results revealed a computed value of 4842.50 and a p-value of 0.001 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the academic performance of students when grouped according to numeracy skills.

This finding implies that performance of learners in their academics varies on the level of their numeracy skills which is factual since one learner might really perform poorly if he or she have poor skills when it comes to numbers as numeracy is one fundamental skill needed to perform well in school. The students' abilities in numeracy have a substantial impact on their overall academic performance. Students with strong numeracy skills tend to perform better academically across various subjects. Their ability to grasp mathematical concepts, solve problems, and apply logical reasoning contributes to their overall academic success. They are often better at analyzing information, making decisions based on data, and solving complex problems.

To support the findings of the study, Guhl (2019) cited that early math and numeracy is the general understanding of numbers and basic mathematical concepts. These are skills such as counting, comparing and contrasting, describing shapes and positions and problem solving. Early math and numeracy skills are the building blocks of all future math classes. Without these skills, students will continue to struggle with higher math concepts. Students need to learn how to solve problems, one of the basic early math skills, for all areas of academics and life outside of school. Early math and numeracy also coincide with language and critical thinking development. More and more, students are entering kindergarten with language deficits and unable to think critically. Students need to be directly taught language skills and critical thinking skills and early math is the perfect way to teach those skills.

Furthermore, Hebres (2023) stated that the numeracy level of the students has a role in their academic performance because numeracy assessment focuses on the application of mathematical concepts learned across multiple subjects from kindergarten to Grade 10.

Being numerates means you have the confidence to use basic fundamental operations (4Fs) and problem solving to use basic concepts in understanding complex topics. Mastering these are the keys to understand and progress in Mathematics especially the complex topics like algebra. It is one of the main focuses of the teachers along with the literacy since these two are the emerging problems of the Department of Education in the Philippines (Gigante, 2020).

Difference in the Academic Performance of Students when they are grouped according to their Learning Style

The table below shows the difference in the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their learning styles.

Table 7. Difference in the Academic Performance of Students when they are grouped according to their Learning Style

Learning Style	n	Mean Rank
Kinesthetic	180	157.12
Visual	73	155.82
Read/Write	28	123.86
Auditory	23	140.65
Total	304	

Computed value (H): 4.00

p-value: 0.262

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table above shows that 180 kinesthetic learners obtained the highest mean rank of 157.12 followed by visual learners with a mean rank of 155.82, while read/write learners obtained the mean rank of 123.86 and auditory learners obtained a mean rank of 140.65.

Using the Kruskal Wallis, the results revealed a computed value of 4.00 and a p-value of 0.262 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of learners when grouped according to their learning style.

The result indicates that academic performance of the students does not vary based on their learning style. This further mean that the way learners prefer to absorb and process information (visual, auditory, kinesthetic, or read/write) does not have a measurable impact

on their overall academic achievement. This suggests that regardless of their learning style whether they are kinesthetic, visual or auditory, students can still perform very well. Learners are complex individuals with unique combinations of abilities, motivations, and backgrounds. Factors such as prior knowledge, interest in the subject, study habits, and support systems can influence academic performance. Other factors, such as teaching quality, curriculum design, and learner engagement, can also play a more critical role in academic performance.

The result disagree with the study of Linca and Matei (2024) which stated that significant differences occur between students with auditory, visual and practical learning styles depending on the academic performance and the year of study. Students' success in the learning process and achieving high academic results can also be influenced by their predominant learning style or the combination of two of the learning styles. Some students may have a predominantly visual learning style and learn through diagrams, pictures, graphs, while others may have an auditory style and learn through lectures (Apud Ariastuti, Wahyudin, 2022; Lincă et al., 2022).

In contrast, Shamsuddin, Kaur (2020) defined learning style as a distinctive way of acquiring knowledge, skills or attitudes through study. For a teacher, learning styles can help identify and solve students' learning problems (Matei, 2021; 2022). This will encourage students to learn more effectively and the teacher will be able to choose educational material that resonates with their learning style.

Difference in the Academic Performance of Students when they are grouped according to their Learning Engagement

The table below shows the difference in the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their learning engagement.

Table 8. *Difference in the Academic Performance of Students when they are grouped according to their Learning Engagement*

<i>Level of Student Engagement</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Very High	56	170.39
High	184	156.92
Moderate	59	125.62
Low	5	106.6
Very Low	0	
Total	304	

Computed value (H): 9.68

p-value: 0.021

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the table in the previous page, students with very high level of engagement obtained a mean rank of 170.39, while students with high level of engagement obtained a mean rank of 156.92, followed by students of moderate level of engagement with a mean rank of 125.62 and students with low level of engagement obtained a mean rank of 106.6.

Using the Kruskal Wallis, results revealed a computed value of 9.68 and a p-value of 0.021 which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the academic performance when grouped in terms of level of engagement of students.

This implies that academic performance of the students varies depending on their level of engagement. This further indicates that the degree to which students are actively involved in their learning process has a substantial impact on their academic outcomes. This suggests that students with high levels of engagement typically show better academic performance. They are more likely to attend classes regularly, participate in discussions, complete assignments on time, and seek help when needed. Their involvement enhances their learning experience and contributes to higher academic performance.

The findings of the study are supported by Delfino (2019) whose study revealed that the level of student engagement along behavioral, emotional and cognitive engagements were high with a mean of 2.84. It was found out that academic performance of the respondents was very good (GWA=1.83). The correlational analysis found that teacher ($r=.125, p=.029$), school ($r=.143, p=.013$), and family factors ($r=.106, p=.028$) were positively related to student engagement, while the Multiple Linear Regression analysis revealed that there was relatively low percentage of variance (1.8%) but shows that the factors were significant predictors of student engagement $F(3, 301)=2.905$. Furthermore, it was found out that behavioral, emotional and cognitive engagements were positively correlated to the academic performance of the students. The teacher, the school, and the parents should have strong collaboration to provide more opportunities for students to maximize their university engagement.

Pairwise Comparison

The table below shows the pairwise comparison between the academic performance of Grade 9 students when they are grouped according to their learning engagement.

Based on the table 9 on the comparison between academic performance in terms of level of learning engagement, low vs moderate obtained a p-value of 0.642 interpreted as not significant while low vs high obtained a p-value of 0.206 interpreted as not significant, low vs very high obtained a p-value of 0.120 interpreted as not significant, and high vs very high obtained a p-value of 0.315 interpreted as not significant. On the other hand, the results revealed that moderate vs high and very high obtained a p-value of 0.017 and 0.006

respectively both interpreted as significant. Thus, it can be implied that there are significant differences on the academic performances of the students with moderate and high level of engagement. The same is true as well to students with moderate and very high level of engagement.

Table 9. *Pairwise Comparison between the Academic Performance of Grade 9 Students when they are grouped according to their Learning Engagement*

Comparison	p-value	Interpretation
Low vs. Moderate	0.642	Not significant
Low vs. High	0.206	Not significant
Low vs. Very High	0.120	Not significant
Moderate vs. High	0.017	Significant
Moderate vs. Very High	0.006	Significant
High vs. Very High	0.315	Not significant

Congruent to the findings of the study, cited in Furtés et al. (2023), student engagement was positively correlated with academic performance. Due to engaged students' high levels of effort and energy investment, dedication to their studies, and frequent immersion in their study activities, engagement is a good predictor of academic performance. Students who consistently focus on their study activities become goal-oriented and more likely to learn effectively. In addition, one of the essential aspects influencing students' performance is their motivation in school. For the educational system to succeed, learners must be motivated to learn.

Relationship between the Numeracy Skill and Academic Performance

The table below shows the relationship between the numeracy skill of Grade 9 students and their academic performance.

Table 10. *Relationship between the Numeracy Skill of Grade 9 Students and their Academic Performance*

Numeracy Skills	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectations	
Numerate	70	87	73	15	0	245
Non-Numerate	5	18	27	9	0	59
Total	75	105	100	24	0	304

Computed value (χ^2): 16.84

p-value: <0.001

Decision: Reject H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Out of 245 numerate students, 70 are on the outstanding level of academic performance, 87 are very satisfactory, 73 are on the level of satisfactory academic performance, and 15 are fairly satisfactory. However, 59 non-numerates, there are only 5 who have outstanding level of academic performance, 18 are very satisfactory, 27 are satisfactory, and nine are fairly satisfactory.

Further, using Chi-square test, the computed value is 16.84 with a p-value of 0.001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the numeracy skills of Grade 9 students and their academic performance. The result of this study implies that the numeracy skill of the students affects their academic performance. The level of their understanding in fundamental arithmetic operations including addition, subtraction, division, and multiplication influence their tendency to achieve educationally and have a profound understanding of the subject matter.

The influence of numeracy abilities on academic performance goes beyond mathematics. The findings suggest that numeracy skills improve students' ability to understand quantitative information in courses such as physics, chemistry, and economics. Furthermore, children with stronger numeracy skills perform better in topics that require logical reasoning and data interpretation. Educators and policymakers emphasize the significance of early numeracy initiatives in supporting students' academic journeys. Schools may assist Grade 9 students achieve academically by offering focused guidance and tools to build numeracy skills, laying a solid foundation for future educational and professional prospects.

The result closely similar with the findings of Callaman & Itaas (2020) that there is a favorable association between improved numerical skills and general mathematics achievement for students.

Relationship between the Learning Styles and Academic Performance

The table below shows the relationship between the learning styles of Grade 9 students and their academic performance.

The table shows that of the 180 respondents who displayed a kinesthetic learning style, 50 of them have outstanding, 63 have very satisfactory, 51 have satisfactory, and 16 have fairly satisfactory level of academic performance. There are 73 visual learners where 19 of them have outstanding, 24 have very satisfactory, 26 have satisfactory, and 4 have fairly satisfactory academic performance. Those who are read and write learners, 2 of them are outstanding, 11 are very satisfactory, 11 are satisfactory, and 4 are fairly satisfactory in their academic performance. Of the 23 who are auditory, there are 4 of them who are outstanding, 7 are very satisfactory, and 12 have satisfactory academic performance.

Table 11. Relationship between the Learning Styles of Grade 9 Students and their Academic Performance

Learning Styles	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectations	
Kinesthetic	50	63	51	16	0	180
Visual	19	24	26	4	0	73
Read/Write	2	11	11	4	0	28
Auditory	4	7	12	0	0	23
Total	75	105	100	24	0	304

Computed value (x2): 13.38
 p-value: 0.146
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Chi-square test, the computed value is 13.38 with a p-value of 0.146 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted which means that there is no significant relationship between the learning style and the academic performance of students.

This finding implies that learning styles have nothing to do with the academic performance of the students. This further suggests that regardless of the learning styles, students can perform very well in academics or very poor on the other hand. They can process and comprehend the lesson regardless of their learning style. They have a deeper understanding of the topic and perform better academically irrespective of the style they learn. Other factors, such as teaching quality, curriculum design, and student engagement, may play a more critical role in academic performance than learning styles.

The result of this study is in disagreement to the claim of Yako (2019) that integrating learning styles into teaching strategies can boost Grade 9 student engagement and achievement. Graphic organizers, diagrams, and films can help visual learners better acquire and retain information. In contrast, auditory learners thrive in situations that allow students to engage in debates, listen to lectures, and use mnemonic techniques. While kinesthetic learners, who enjoy hands-on activities and movement, often get better results from interactive tests and physical demonstrations (Jonas, 2018), tailoring educational strategies to these different learning styles can lead to increased student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement while matching teaching approaches to learning styles may be beneficial, the evidence for their usefulness is mixed, and a balanced approach that incorporates multiple types may be most effective in serving diverse learners (Yako, 2019).

It also contradicts to the study of Lew (2024) which highlights the ongoing discussion about the impact of learning styles on academic success. While some research suggests that aligning teaching approaches with learning styles can boost academic achievement and attitudes toward learning, others show only minor effects. Nonetheless, understanding and catering to varied learning styles has the potential to improve learning outcomes by allowing students to engage with knowledge in their preferred ways.

Furthermore, the findings of this study deviate to the research of Magulod (2019) which demonstrates substantial links between learning styles, study habits, and academic success among students enrolled in applied science courses. The findings indicate that instructional interventions targeted to students' learning styles and study habits can boost academic performance. These interventions include introducing a variety of teaching and learning activities, training faculty on successful teaching tactics, and giving seminars to help students improve their study habits.

Moreover, the result of this study is in conflict to the statement of Chetty et al. (2019) that aligning teaching approaches with students' learning styles improves learning experiences and academic performance. Mismatched teaching and learning styles can lead to student unhappiness and even jeopardize academic achievement. Students' reactions to teaching styles influence the variety of teaching and learning approaches, resulting in both matches and mismatches between instructors' methods and students' preferences.

Relationship between the Level of Student Engagement and Academic Performance

The table below shows the relationship between the level of engagement of Grade 9 students and their academic performance.

Table 12. Relationship between the Level of Engagement of Grade 9 Students and their Academic Performance

Level of Student Engagement	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectations	
Very High	18	21	14	3	0	56
High	49	63	58	14	0	184
Moderate	7	21	24	7	0	59
Low	1	0	4	0	0	5
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	75	105	100	24	0	304

Computed value (G): 0.25
 p-value: 0.001
 Decision: Reject Ho
 Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that there are 56 students who have a very high level of engagement. Of the 56, there are 18 who display an outstanding academic performance, 21 are very satisfactory, 14 are satisfactory, and three are fairly satisfactory. On the other hand, of the 184 students who reveals a high level of engagement, 49 of them are outstanding in their academic performance, 63 are very satisfactory, 58 are satisfactory, and 14 are fairly satisfactory. However, there are 59 students who claim that they have a moderate level of student engagement. Of these 59, seven of them have an outstanding academic performance, 21 are very satisfactory, 24 are satisfactory, and seven are fairly satisfactory. There are five students who have a low level of student engagement where one of them display an outstanding academic performance and four of them performs satisfactorily.

Using Goodman Kruskal's Gamma Coefficient, the computed value is 0.25 and the P-value of 0.001 is lower than 0.05 level of significance, rejecting the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant relationship between the level of engagement of Grade 9 students and their academic performance.

According to the findings, the link between student involvement and academic accomplishment is well established, implying that higher levels of engagement are substantially connected with better academic outcomes. Thus, student engagement consists of emotional, behavioral, and cognitive components, such as students' enthusiasm for learning, active participation in classroom activities, and in-depth processing of educational content. Engaged students are more likely to work hard, overcome challenges, and have a positive attitude about their studies, all of which lead to academic achievement.

The findings is in consonance with the statement of de Vries & Martínez (2019) that improving student motivation and performance requires creating an engaging learning environment with interactive teaching methods, relevant material, and supportive relationships. As a result, encouraging high levels of engagement through tailored educational techniques and supportive learning environments is crucial to increasing academic performance and fostering long-term educational success.

This is also in connection with the report of Pendon (2022) that engaged students had better academic performance, fewer dropouts, and a stronger connection to their educational experience. Grade 9 is a critical year for adolescents, and student involvement levels can have a significant impact on academic success and future educational paths. Pendon (2022) defines engagement as students' investment in learning activities, emotional commitment to school, and involvement in academic and extracurricular activities. This involvement is crucial because it is linked to higher academic achievement, fewer dropouts, and better psychological well-being.

There are several aspects that influence student participation in Grade nine. The transition to high school typically brings additional academic challenges and social difficulties, making it a crucial moment to encourage engagement. Khan et al. (2020) underlines the importance of creating optimal learning environments that promote student engagement through interactive, student-centered training. Furthermore, the research underlines the importance of fostering teacher-student relationships, with studies showing that students who feel respected and understood by their instructors are more willing to participate (Otoum, 2021). A classroom environment that fosters autonomy, competence, and relatedness can significantly boost engagement levels, resulting in improved academic performance and personal growth for Grade 9 students (Christensen et al., 2020).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn;

Most of the students are proficient in utilizing mathematical concepts to solve practical problems and understand basic arithmetic operations.

The most common learning style of the respondents is kinesthetic.

The Grade 9 students show great level of attention, interest, excitement, optimism, and passion that students show when learning or being taught.

The Grade 9 students have very satisfactory academic performance.

The academic performance of the students varies in terms of their numeracy level,

Students' performance in academics does not differs depending on their learning styles.

Academically, the students perform differently in terms of their level of learning engagement.

The level of student's understanding in fundamental arithmetic operations including addition, subtraction, division, and multiplication influence their academic performance

The learning style of the Grade 9 students do not affect their academic performance. They can process and comprehend the lesson regardless of their learning style.

The association between learning engagement and academic accomplishment is well established showing that higher levels of engagement are substantially connected with better academic outcomes.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are stated for the favorable action of the concerned:

Education Program Specialists can implement focused numeracy programs that aim to improve core mathematical skills. These may include tutoring after-school programs, summer math classes, and incorporating numeracy exercises into normal classroom procedures.

Teachers may use individualized instruction to adapt on how their students learn (visual, auditory, and kinesthetic) to improve understanding and retention of material. Learning strategies and educational materials can be diverse and inclusive, catering to the dominant kinesthetic learning preference while also providing adequate resources for visual, read and write, and auditory learners to ensure a comprehensive and effective learning experience for all. For example, visual learners benefit from graphs and charts, while auditory learners benefit from talks Hands-on activities benefit kinesthetic learners as well as lecturers.

Teachers are encouraged to continue in providing active learning and student involvement, and use active learning tactics including group projects, interactive activities, and technological integration to boost student participation.

School administrators may continue to provide professional development for teachers by offering programs that focus on effective numeracy teaching practices, supporting varied learning styles, and enhancing student engagement. Encourage group activities and collaborative projects that require numeracy skills. Peer learning can be an effective way for students to develop and strengthen their skills.

The faculty members can use more student-centered teaching strategies. These strategies may provide opportunities to students to maximize their engagement in the teaching and learning process.

Schools may design a training/seminar on effective student-centered teaching strategies for the faculty members. An intervention program can be designed to improving numeracy skills, accommodating various learning styles, and increasing learning engagement

The teachers may conduct enhancement activities specifically in mathematics to help the learners master and improve the numeracy skills. Design training and workshops to the teachers in secondary to improve the new techniques in teaching numeracy to the students

Teachers may use Data-Driven Approaches to monitor improvement to track student improvement in numeracy, learner engagement, and academic performance. They may use assessments and analytics to identify areas that require improvement and customize solutions accordingly.

Future researchers may also conduct similar study and may include other variable that may affect the academic performance of students.

References

- Admin. (2023). What is the VARK Learning Style Model? Harappa. <https://harappa.education/harappa-diaries/vark-learning-style/>
- Alarcon, N. A., & Abanto, R. G. (2024). Correlates of numeracy skills of Grade 7 students in Dominador Narido High School: Basis for intervention. *IRE Journals*, 7(9), 48. ISSN: 2456-8880.
- Almoslamani, Y. (2022). The impact of learning strategies on the academic achievement of university students in Saudi Arabia. *Learning & Teaching in Higher Education: Gulf Perspectives*, 18(1), 4–18. <https://doi.org/10.1108/lthe-08-2020-0025>
- Anu_V. (2023). Visual Learning Style: Strategies and Benefits - Embibe. Embibe Exams. <https://www.embibe.com/exams/visual-learning-benefits-and-strategies-for-students-teachers/>
- Arafah, K., Sutiawati, M. D., Sudirman, R., Arafah, B., & Arafah, A. N. (2020). The Development of Guided Inquiry-Based Learning Worksheet Assisted by Livewire Simulations In Alternating Current. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*.
- Arthurs JB. A juggling act in the classroom: managing different learning styles. *Teach Learn Nurs*. 2007;2(1):2–7.
- Atienza, A., Barradas, M. J., & Hernandez, J. (2019). Level of Numeracy skills of Grade 11 students: Basis for Proposed Numeracy tools. <https://ojs.Aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/8764>
- Baafi, R. K. A. (2020). Effect of instructional strategies on students' academic achievement in public senior high schools in Ghana. *International Journal of Education*, 12(2), 17. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ije.v12i2.16978>
- Bay Atlantic University. (2022). Read and Write Learners: Techniques & Tips. Bay Atlantic University - Washington, D.C. <https://bau.edu/blog/read-and-write-learners/>
- Bay Atlantic University. (2022). What is a kinesthetic learner? Bay Atlantic University - Washington, D.C. <https://bau.edu/blog/kinesthetic-learner/>
- Behera, S. K. (n.d.). The merits and Demerits of Lecture Method of teaching. https://www.academia.edu/6856603/The_Merits_and_Demerits_of_Lecture_Method_of_Teaching
- Belleza, M. J. A. (2022). Numeracy Level of Non-Numerate Learners through Enhanced Mathematics Learning Kits with Parental Involvement at Homes. Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6922388>
- Bhasin, H. (2019). Collaborative Learning: What it is, Benefits and Examples. *Marketing* 91.

<https://www.marketing91.com/collaborative-learning/>

Brallier, C. (2020). The effects of Student Engagement on Academic Achievement Among College Students. Retrieved from <https://jewelscholar.mtsu.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/4a1228df-60f6-4cec-acbd-cfadff8756d0/content>

Brew, E. A., Nketiah, B., & Koranteng, R. (2021). A Literature Review of Academic Performance, an Insight into Factors and their Influences on Academic Outcomes of Students at Senior High Schools. *OALib*, 08(06), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1107423>

Briones, Leonor M. (2019). Addressing the Challenge of Quality in Basic Education. Speech at the Launch of Sulong EduKalidad Bulwagan ng Karunungan, Department of Education.

Callaman, & Itaas. (2020). Students' Mathematics achievement in Mindanao context: A meta-analysis . Eric. from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1267489.pdf>

Calma, J. D. (2018). Specialized Strategies for Non-Numerate Grade Seven Students in Facilitating Learning Number Sense. The Summit 2018. <https://rpo.ua.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/2.-Summit-2018-Specialized-Strategies-34-59.pdf>

Chaudhari, A. (2021). What is Descriptive Research Design? Voxco. <https://www.voxco.com/blog/descriptive-research-design/>

Christensen, M., Dyrstad, J. M., & Innstrand, S. T. (2020). Academic work engagement, resources and productivity: empirical evidence with policy implications. *Studies in Higher Education*, 45(1), 86–99. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2018.1517304>

Christine, A. B., Billiah, G., & Jared, N. A. (2019). Influence of Teaching Methods on Students' Academic

Christine, et.al, (2019). Kiswahili Subject in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Lang'ata Subcounty. *African Research Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 6(2), 2019 ISSN (online): 2312-0134 | Website: www.arjess.org

Cognitive Load Theory (John Sweller) – Instructional Design.org. (2018). Instructional Design.org. <https://www.instructionaldesign.org/theories/cognitive-load/>

Coronacion, A. A. (2024). Improving the numeracy level of grade five learners through project math-yaga. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/IMPROVING-THE-NUMERACY-LEVEL-OF-GRADE-FIVE-LEARNERS-Coronacion/3049e6f0c727fbabeb709af0a09bb5dbd03262f7>

de Vries, W., & Martínez, O. G. (2019). Performance, productivity and the diversity of student pathways. *Higher Education Forum*, 16(March), 45–68. <https://doi.org/10.15027/47549>

Delfino, A. P. (2019). Student Engagement and Academic Performance of Students of Partido State University. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 15(1). Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1222588.pdf?fbclid=>

DepEd RM 1092 (2023). Guidelines on the Utilization of the Enhanced Regional Unified Numeracy Test (E RUNT) for key stages 2, 3 & 4. <https://region8.deped.gov.ph/2023/10/06/october-06-2023-rm-1092-s-2023-guidelines-on-the-utilization-of-the-enhanced-regional-unified-numeracy-test-erunt-for-key-stages-2-3-4/>

Dmitrichenkova, S. V. (2020). Learning styles and teaching methods. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2020.12.02.6>

Dong, A., Jong, M. S., & King, R. B. (2020). How does prior knowledge influence learning engagement? The mediating roles of cognitive load and Help-Seeking. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.591203>

Eads, A. (2022). What is the auditory learning style? (With key strategies). Indeed.com. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/auditory-learning-style>

Elopre, M. G., & Baggay, C. (2022). Numeracy through Literacy: Basis for an Enhancement Program for the Grade 7 Learners of Barasoain Memorial. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23333.58081>

Escuadro, S. (2023). Learning styles: why they're important in learning and development. *EdApp Microlearning*. <https://www.edapp.com/blog/why-learning-styles-are-important/>

Experiential learning - world learning (2023). *World Learning*. <https://www.Worldlearning.org/approach/experiential-learning/>

Experiential Learning | Center for Teaching & Learning. (n.d.). © 2024 Boston University. https://www.bu.edu/ctl/ctl_resource/experiential-learning/

Faingold (2022). UNICEF chief urges PH to recover learning losses from the covid-19 pandemic. <https://www.pids.gov.ph/details>

Feder, M. (2023). What is curriculum and instruction in education? University of Phoenix. <https://www.phoenix.edu/blog/curriculum-and-instruction-in-education.html>

Fleming, G. (2020). The auditory learning style. *ThoughtCo*. <https://www.thoughtco.com/auditory-learning-style-p3-3212038>

Fuertes, H. G., Evangelista Jr., I. A., Marcellones, I. J. Y., & Bacatan, J. R. (2023). Student engagement, academic motivation, and academic performance of intermediate-level students. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, 10(3), 133-149. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8037103.

Gcu. (2020). How to recognize and support learning styles in the classroom. GCU. <https://www.gcu.edu/blog/teaching-school-administration/how-recognize-and-support-learning-styles-classroom>

Goalcast. (2022). Your Learning Strategy Might Be Completely Wrong – Let’s Fix It. Goalcast. <https://www.goalcast.com/visual-learning-style-strategies/>

Guhl, P. (2019). The Impact of Early Math and Numeracy Skills on Academic in Elementary School. Master's Theses & Capstone Projects. Northwestern College, Iowa. https://nwcommons.nwciowa.edu/education_masters/155/

Han, F. (2021). The Relations between Teaching Strategies, Students’ Engagement in Learning, and Teachers’ Self-Concept. *Sustainability*, 13(9), 5020. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095020>

Haramain, J., & Alih, S. K. (2021). Instructional strategies employed by public elementary school teachers in south central Mindanao, Philippines. ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350785305>

Hattie, J. A., & Anderman, E. (2019). *International guide to student achievement* (2nd ed.). Routledge.

Hebres, R. B. (2022). Academic performance and numeracy level of Grade 10 students in mathematics. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 12(2), 550-554. Retrieved from <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v12i2/SR23123131547.pdf>

Herrity, J. (2023). 11 Benefits of Collaborative Learning (Plus Tips to use it). Indeed.com. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/benefits-of-collaborative-learning>

Heward, W. L., & Twyman, J. S. (2021). Teach More in Less Time: Introduction to the special section on Direct Instruction. *Behavior Analysis in Practice*, 14(3), 763–765. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40617-021-00639-8>

Hodges, B. T. (2018). School engagement is more than just talk. Gallup.com. <https://www.gallup.com/education/244022/school-engagement-talk.aspx>

Howley-Rouse, A. (2020) An introduction to engagement in educational settings. THE EDUCATION HUB. <https://theeducationhub.org.nz/an-introduction-to-engagement-in-educational-settings/>

Husaini, Y. A., & Shukor, N. S. A. (2023). Factors Affecting Students’ Academic Performance: A review. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367360842_Factors_Affecting_Students'_Academic_Performance_A_review

Ignacio, A. N., Ramos, T. A., & Syguia, J. N. (2020). "The Journey to Learning: Through the learning styles of the Senior High School Academic Strand students. Research Gate. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10443.62240>

İlçin, N., Tomruk, M., Yeşilyaprak, S. S., Karadibak, D., & Savcı, S. (2018). The relationship between learning styles and academic performance in TURKISH physiotherapy students. *BMC Medical Education*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-018-1400-2>

Imran, Khan and Aslam (2023) Title: “Development and Validation of Student Engagement Questionnaire”. <https://vark-learn.com>

Indeed Editorial Team. (2024). Numeracy Skills: Definition and Examples. Indeed Career Guide. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/finding-a-job/numeracy-skills>

Institute for Experiential Learning. (2023). What is experiential learning? - Institute for Experiential Learning. <https://experientiallearninginstitute.org/what-is-experiential-learning/>

ipl.org. (2020). Benefits of direct instruction. 1307 Words | Internet Public Library. <https://www.ipl.org/essay/Benefits-Of-Direct-Instruction-PK5F6V74SJP6>

Isa, S. G., Mammam, M. A., Bala, Y. A., & Badar, Y. (2022). The Impact Of Teaching Methods On Academic Performance Of Secondary School Students In Nigeria. ResearchGate. <https://doi.org/10.37118/ijdr.18223.07.2020>

Jean Piaget Learning Theory of Constructivism in Education» Education Summary. (n.d.). Education Summary. <https://educationsummary.com/lesson/jean-piaget-learning-theory-of-constructivism-in-education/>

Jenna. (2021). Kinesthetic Learner: Characteristics, learning Strategies, & activities. BJU Press Blog. <https://blog.bjupress.com/blog/2021/11/30/kinesthetic-learner-characteristics-learning-strategies-activities/>

Jonas, N. (2018). Numeracy Practices and Numeracy Skills Among Adults. *Education Working Paper*, 177(177), 1–74. www.oecd.org/edu/workingpapers

Kapur, R. (2020). Lecture Method: The Comprehensively used Pedagogical Method. ResearchGate.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345893936_Lecture_Method_The_Comprehensively_used_Pedagogical_Method

Karikari A. et al., (2020). Causes of students poor performance in Mathematics. A case of Sefwi Bonwire D/A junior high school in the western region of Ghana. <https://www.journalijar.com/article/34668/causes-of-students-poorperformancein-mathematics.-a-case-of-sefwi-bonwire-d/a-junior-high-school-in-the-western-region-of-ghana/>

Kaysar, A. (2022). What is Academic Success (Student Learning)? - Peers and pedagogy. Peers and Pedagogy. <https://achievethecore.org/peersandpedagogy/what-is-academic-success/>

Kelly, M. (2019). Advantages and Disadvantages of lecturing. Thought Co. <https://www.thoughtco.com/lecture-pros-and-cons-8037>

Khan, M. J., Ashraf, A., & Nadeem, A. (2020). The Effect of Time Management on the Academic Performance of Students in the Higher Educational Institutions of Islamabad. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 9(3), 202–211. [https://doi.org/10.30543/9-3\(2020\)-16](https://doi.org/10.30543/9-3(2020)-16)

Kurt, S. (2022). Direct Instruction: What is It? What are Its Key Principles? Education Library. <https://educationlibrary.org/direct-instruction-what-is-it-what-are-its-key-principles/>

Landicho, R. R. (2021). Factors affecting performance in general Mathematics of grade eleven students in Talumpok integrated school: basis for intervention activities action research. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 6(1), 618-626. <http://bitly.ws/9nMw>

Lazaro, M. R., Jr. (2020). The Advance Generation: The Relationship Between The Instructional Approches And Academic Performance In Oral Communication Of Grade 11 Students Of Norzagaray National Highschool. <https://www.academia.edu/45049524/>

Lew, M. (2024). The Effect of Learning Style Types on a Student's Academics. *International Schooling*. <https://internationalschooling.org/blog/the-effect-of-learning-style-types-on-a-students-academics/>

Liem, G. a. D. (2019). Academic performance and assessment. *Educational Psychology*, 39(6), 705–708. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2019.1625522>

Linca, F. I. and Matei, F. L. (2024). Learning Styles and Academic Performance Among Students. *Land Forces Academy Review*. 29(1):63-68. DOI:10.2478/raft-2024-0006.

Llego, M. A. (2022). Differentiated Instruction: A How-To Guide for Teachers. TeacherPH. <https://www.teacherph.com/differentiated-instruction-guide-teachers/>

Llego, M. A. (2022). Inquiry-Based Learning: What it is and why you should use it. TeacherPH. <https://www.teacherph.com/inquiry-based-learning/>

Loveless, B. (2024). Experiential Learning: The Complete guide. Education Corner. <https://www.educationcorner.com/experiential-learning-guide/>

Macaranas, J. R. (2022). APPRECIATING THE LECTURE METHOD. https://www.academia.edu/69093487/APPRECIATING_THE_LECTURE_METHOD

Magulod, G. C. (2019). Learning styles, study habits and academic performance of Filipino University students in applied science courses: Implications for instruction. *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, 9(2), 184. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jotse.504>

Main, P. (2023). Direct Instruction: A teacher's guide. Structural Learning. <https://www.structural-learning.com/post/direct-instruction-a-teachers-guide>

Makondo P. et al., (2020). Causes of poor academic performance in Mathematics at ordinary level: A case of Mavuzani high school, Zimbabwe. [https://www.ijhssi.org/papers/vol9\(6\)/Series-1/C0906011018.pdf](https://www.ijhssi.org/papers/vol9(6)/Series-1/C0906011018.pdf)

Malvik, C. (2024). 4 Types of learning styles: How to accommodate a diverse group of students. Rasmussen University. <https://www.rasmussen.edu/degrees/education/blog/types-of-learning-styles/>

Me, C. (2020). What is differentiated instruction and why is it important? -. . . Exceptional Thinkers. <https://teachingexceptionalthinkers.com/2020/02/25/what-is-differentiated-instruction/>

Meador, D. (2019). Using effective instructional strategies. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/building-an-arsenal-of-effective-instructional-strategies-3194257>

Mebert, L., Barnes, R., Dalley, J., Gawarecki, L., Ghazi-Nezami, F., Shafer, G., Slater, J., & Yezbick, E. (2020). Fostering student engagement through a real-world, collaborative project across disciplines and institutions. *Higher Education Pedagogies*, 5(1), 30–51. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23752696.2020.1750306>

Mebert, L., Barnes, R., Dalley, J., Gawarecki, L., Ghazi-Nezami, F., Shafer, G., Slater, J., & Yezbick, E. (2020). Fostering student engagement through a real-world, collaborative project across disciplines and institutions. *Higher Education Pedagogies*, 5(1), 30–51. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23752696.2020.1750306>

Mndawe, J. (2024). The Auditory Learning Style - Characteristics and study Strategies. Teach Me 2. <https://www.teachme2.com/enza/blog?p=the-auditory-learning-style-characteristics-and-study-strategies>

Modishproject. (2018). A Critical Analysis On Corelation Between Learning Style And Academic Performance Of Students. Modish Project. <https://www.modishproject.com/learning-style-academic-students/>

Morrow, P. (2022). Importance of Numeracy Skills - Maths Academy. Maths Academy. <https://www.mathsacademy.com.au/importance-of-numeracy-skills/>

Mountford H, Jones S, Tucker B. Learning styles of entry-level physiotherapy students. *Adv Physiother*. 2006;8 (Suppl 3):128–36.

MSEd, K. C. (2022). What is Self-Determination Theory? Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-self-determination-theory-2795387>

MSEd, K. C. (2023). Overview of VARK learning styles. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/vark-learning-styles-2795156>

Munir, N., Ahmad, N., & Hussain, S. (2018). Relationship of learning styles and academic performance of secondary school students. ResearchGate. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326972212>

National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments. (2022). Engagement. Retrieved from <https://safesupportivelearning.ed.gov/topic-research/engagement>

Newham, T. (2023). Learner engagement: definition, benefits and challenges. Think Learning. <https://www.think-learning.com/employee-engagement/learner-engagement/>

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Niyati, S., (2021). How to assess a student's learning styles. <https://www.classcardapp.com/blog/how-to-assess-a-students-learning-styles>

Nja, C. O., Umali, C. B., Asuquo, E. E., & Orim, R. E. (2019). The Influence of Learning Styles on Academic Performance among Science Education Undergraduates at the University of Calabar. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1236177>

Oke, A. A. (2020). Teachers' Teaching Methods and Students' Academic Performances in Ibarapa East Local Government Area Secondary Schools. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research. Arts, Humanities and Education*, 6(10), 15-28.

Onzi, S. H., Mugizi, W., Rwothumio, J., & Mugenyi, D. K. (2023). Teaching Approaches and Student Engagement in Secondary Schools in Arua City, Uganda. *East African Journal of Education Studies*,6(2), 85-103.

Patel, D. (2020). Instructional methods and strategies. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359648503_Instructional_Methods_and_Strategies

Pendon, R. P. (2022). Self-Efficacy and Mathematics Performance Among College Students: Basis for Development of Mathematics Engagement Training. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 13(S01), 1697–1705. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pnr.2022.13.s01.203>

Pennsylvania Department of Education. (2024). Academic engagement and support. Department of Education. <https://www.education.pa.gov/Schools/safeschools/SchoolClimate/SCIP/ActionPlanning/Pages/AcademicEngagement.aspx>

Percipio Global Ltd. (2024). Collaborative learning approaches | EEF. EEF. <https://educationendowmentfoundation.org.uk/education-evidence/teaching-learning-toolkit/collaborative-learning-approaches>

Performance in Kiswahili Subject in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Lang'ata Sub-county. *African Research Journal of Educational and Social Sciences*, 6(2), 16-24.

Persaud, C. (2018). *Instructional Strategies: The Ultimate Guide*. Toronto, Canada.

Persaud, C. (2023). 25 Effective instructional Strategies for Educators. Top Hat. <https://tophat.com/blog/instructional-strategies/>

Pitogo, S., & Oco, R. (2023). Pupils' numeracy skills and mathematics performance. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373110905_Pupils'_Numeracy_Skills_and_Mathematics_Performance

- Pitogo, S., & Oco, R. (2023). Pupils' numeracy skills and mathematics performance. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373110905_Pupils'_Numeracy_Skills_and_Mathematics_Performance
- Promethean World. (2022). 12 active learning strategies in the classroom. <https://www.prometheanworld.com/gb/resource-centre/blogs/12-active-learning-strategies-in-the-classroom/>
- Promethean World. (2023). What is a reading and writing learning style? <https://www.prometheanworld.com/resource-center/blogs/what-is-a-reading-and-writing-learning-style/>
- Quinn-Nilas, C., Kennett, D., & Maki, K. E. (2019). Examining explanatory style for failure of direct entry and transfer students using structural equation modeling. *Educational Psychology, 39*(6), 749–767. doi:10.1080/01443410.2019.1574340
- Ramsden P. Learning to teach in higher education. Oxon: Routledge; 2003.
- Renard, L (2023). Direct instruction - A practical guide to effective teaching. BookWidgets. <https://www.bookwidgets.com/blog/2019/03/direct-instruction-a-practical-guide-to-effective-teaching>
- Riawan A., Suyatna A., Herlina, K. (2019). Practicality and Effectiveness of Student Worksheets Using Inquiry-Based Learning Assisted by basic Mathematics Skills to Develop Critical Thinking. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology- ISSN No:-2456-2165. Volume 4, Issue 8.*
- Roell, K. (2018). The Kinesthetic Learning Style: Traits and study Strategies. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/the-kinesthetic-learning-style-3212046>
- Roell, K. (2019). The visual learning style. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/visual-learning-style-3212062>
- Rolljak.com. (2023). How the School Experience Affects Student Engagement and What Can You Do About It. Retrieved from <https://www.rolljak.com/blog/how-the-school-experience-affects-student-engagement-and-what-can-you-do>
- S Otoum, F. A. (2021). Influence of Teachers' Job Satisfaction on Student Academic Performance: a Case Study of Teachers in Jerash Governorate. *20*(5), 5294–5301. <https://doi.org/10.17051/ilkonline.2021.05.593>
- Sa'dijah, C., Purnomo, H., Abdullah, A. H., Permadi, H., Anwar, L., Cahyowati, E. T. D., & Sa'diyah, M. (2023). Students' numeracy skills in solving numeracy tasks: Analysis of students of junior high schools. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0113664>
- Saunders, L., & Wong, M. A. (2020). Active learning: engaging people in the learning process. Pressbooks. <https://iopn.library.illinois.edu/pressbooks/instructioninlibraries/chapter/active-learning-engaging-people-in-the-learning-process/>
- Scholl, A., & Scholl, A. (2023). What is “Inquiry-Based Learning”? Types, benefits, examples. *SplashLearn Blog – Educational Resources for Parents, Teachers & Kids*. <https://www.splashlearn.com/blog/what-is-inquiry-based-learning-a-complete-overview/>
- Schuler, M. (2024). What is Inquiry-Based Learning? A guide for educators. *We Are Teachers*. <https://www.weareteachers.com/inquiry-based-learning/>
- Shamas, J. (2021). What is a Reading/Writing Learning Style? *Anything Academic*. <https://library.anythingacademic.com/learning-styleworles/learning-styles-reading-writing-learners/>
- Staake, J. (2023). What are instructional strategies, and how should teachers use them? *We Are Teachers*. <https://www.weareteachers.com/instructional-strategies/>
- Staff, S., & Staff, S. (2023). Active Learning: How to implement it in classroom in 2023. *SimpleK12.com*. <https://www.simplek12.com/learning-theories-strategies/active-learning/>
- Staff, S., & Staff, S. (2023). Visual Learning Guide to Understanding Visual Learners. *SimpleK12.com*. <https://www.simplek12.com/learning-theories-strategies/visual-learning/>
- Staff, T. (2023). 7 types of learning styles and how you can to teach them. *Teachable*. <https://teachable.com/blog/types-of-learning-styles>
- Staff, W. a. T. (2023). What is differentiated instruction and what does it look like in the classroom? *We Are Teachers*. <https://www.weareteachers.com/what-is-differentiated-instruction/>
- State of Victoria, Department of Education and Training. (2020). Issues in the Teaching of Mathematics: Critical Connections Between Numeracy and Mathematics. https://research.acer.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1030&context=learning_processes
- Steele, A. (2021). What is active learning and what are the benefits? | Cambridge. *Brighter Thinking Blog | Cambridge University Press*. <https://www.cambridge.org/us/education/blog/2019/06/25/what-active-learning-and-what-are-benefits/>

- Tatomir, J. (2023). Student engagement: Theory, Levels & Examples. *Psychology Courses / Life Span Developmental Psychology: Homework Help Resource*. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/student-engagement-definition-theory-quiz.html>
- Terry, B. (2022). Tactile-Kinesthetic Learning – Scholar Within. *Scholar Within*. <https://scholarwithin.com/tactile-kinesthetic-learning>
- Tes Magazine. What is direct instruction? (2022). <https://www.tes.com/magazine/tes-explains/what-direct-instruction>
- The Effect of Learning Styles on Academic Achievement in Different Forms of Teaching Ivana Cimermanová 2018 *International Journal of Instruction*. Vol.11, No.3 e-ISSN: 1308-1470. www.e-iji.net
- Thompson, L. (2023). The importance of student engagement: Why active participation is essential for learning. Retrieved from <https://eduengagement.com/posts/the-importance-of-student-engagement/>
- Thornton, T. (2022). What means academic performance? *CLJ*. <https://communityliteracy.org/what-means-academic-performance/>
- Top Hat. (2019). Learning Style Definition and Meaning | Top hat. <https://tophat.com/glossary/l/learning-style/>
- Top Hat. (2019). Visual Learning Definition and Meaning | Top hat. <https://tophat.com/glossary/v/visual-learning/>
- Tucker, G. C. (2023). What is differentiated instruction? *Understood*. <https://www.understood.org/en/articles/differentiated-instruction-what-you-need-to-know>
- Tucker, G. C. (2024). What is differentiated instruction? *Understood*. <https://www.understood.org/en/articles/differentiated-instruction-what-you-need-to-know>
- University of Washington. (2024). Active learning - Teaching@UW. *Teaching@UW*. <https://teaching.washington.edu/engaging-students/active-learning/>
- Valamis. (2023). Collaborative learning. *Valamis*. <https://www.valamis.com/hub/collaborative-learning>
- Valchev, M. (2023). Numeracy Skills: Definition, Development, List, & More. *Business Skills, Software and Knowledge You Truly Need*. <https://www.businessphrases.net/numeracy-skills/>
- VARK Learn Limited. (2023). The VARK Modalities: Visual, Aural, Read/write & Kinesthetic. *VARK - Helping You Learn Better*. <https://vark-learn.com/introduction-to-vark/the-vark-modalities/>
- Vizoso, C., Arias, O., & Rodríguez Pérez, C. (2019). Exploring coping and optimism as predictors of academic burnout and performance among university students. *Educational Psychology*, 39(6), 768-783. doi:10.1080/01443410.2018.1545996
- Western Governors University. What is tactile learning? (2022, October 25). <https://www.wgu.edu/blog/what-tactile-learning2008.html>
- Worgan, M. (2023). Inquiry-based learning: make your classroom more inclusive. *World of Better Learning | Cambridge University Press*. <https://www.cambridge.org/elt/blog/2023/01/08/inquiry-based-learning-make-your-classroom-more-inclusive/>
- Yako, M. J.-M. (2019). Study Habits and Learning Styles As Correlates of Grade 11 Students' Academic Performance in Mathematical Literacy in the Amatole Education District. 5–10. https://www.minsal.cl/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/2019.01.23_PLAN-NACIONAL-DE-CANCER_web.pdf
- Yang, C. (2022). Active Learning: Techniques to Improve Learner Engagement. Retrieved from <https://accelerate.uofuhealth.utah.edu/leadership/active-learning-techniques-to-improve-learner-engagement>
- Yousafzai, A. (2024). The power of direct instruction for effective teaching. *ZONE OF EDUCATION*. <https://zonofeducation.com/direct-instruction/>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Joeveline P. Chrisman

Emiliano Lizares National High School
Department of Education – Philippines